

A Review of e-Waste management and its Challenges in Kenya

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Abstract

The main objective of this paper was to provide an overview of the current state of e-waste management in Kenya. The study constitutes literature reviews of electronic articles published since the year 2011, sourced from journals, media and organizational websites. The review examined various aspects of e-waste management such as product recovery, material recovery, energy recovery, and safe disposal practices. Besides highlighting the extent of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE), the paper outlines the risks presented by unregulated and improper disposal of e-waste and provides recommendations for improving e-waste management in Kenya. The recommendations from the study includes the involvement of the informal sector and other stakeholders in raising awareness of the risks associated with rudimentary e-waste treatment, proposing policy adjustments that considers wide stakeholder participation, and introduction of training programs in technical colleges and universities specifically addressing the issue of WEEE. It further proposes initiatives both at the national and county levels that would foster discussions and debates on e-waste menace with a view of minimizing adverse effects on humans and the environment. This is expected to help Kenya in the advancement of several goals including Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), vision 2030, and meet its constitutional obligations.

Keywords: e-Waste, Electronic Waste, WEEE, e-Waste Management, Kenya

1. INTRODUCTION

The safe disposal of electrical and electronic waste (e-waste) has been a challenge that predates the 1980s but has recently received increased attention globally, because of the exponential growth in the production and utilization of electrical and electronic products (EEPs) (Kimeli, 2014; Kumar & Holuszko, 2016). Locally, despite being a relatively recent addition to the category of serious hazardous waste, it has received significant research limelight because of the challenges it poses on human health and the environment if not properly managed (Songa & Lubanga, 2015; Kaloki, 2014; Tocho & Waema, 2013).

Global technological revolution, consumerism behaviour exhibited by users of EEPs, improved disposable income and the deteriorating quality and lifespan of imported EEPs are some of the factors that have collectively made WEEE the fastest growing waste stream in the world (Lundgren, 2012, Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023; Kwame, 2021).

In Kenya, the problem has been exacerbated by the exponential growth in the application of mobile phones, the government's industrialization programme and adoption of solar powered equipment (Odenyo, 2022). The covid-19 pandemic caused a further spike in the utilization of information communication technology (ICT) and the associated electronic devices because many businesses went online (Ngila, 2020; Adejumo & Oluduro, 2021). More recently, Kenya transferred several government services onto e-platform in its digitization process requiring its citizenry to obtain and pay for the services electronically in what may further increase e-waste volumes in the near future. Due to the anticipated increase of e-waste, there is a lot pressure for underdeveloped countries to come up with environmentally robust e-waste management systems and sound policy initiatives so as to forestall the imminent e-waste disposal crisis occasioned by the increased uptake and imports of electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) (Asante et al, 2019). As of the year 2012, up to 80% of e-waste generated in the developed countries ended up in developing countries for disposal, often disguised as donations by foreign organizations (Lundgren, 2012; Balasubramanian et al., 2019).

The UN adopted sustainable development goals (SDGs) aspires to protect the environment and ensure good health and well-being of humanity. This underscore and prioritizes the need for management of WEEE which is a cross-cutting issue in the SDGs (Forti et al., 2020).

To realise the globally acclaimed circular-economy model e-waste must receive considerable attention (Mbuthia, 2023; Sravastav et al., 2023). Developed countries have successfully demonstrated that sustainable and sound e-waste management is feasible. This is evident in countries like Japan, Switzerland and Canada where management models such as 'take-back systems' are fully established and functional (Africa Clean Energy, 2019; Kumar & Holuszko, 2016). In Canada, the Canadian government regularly conducts audits and issues licenses to recycling and refurbishing firms to operate within a government regulated framework (Kumar & Holuszko, 2016). Ghana as case of a developing nation has implemented a comparatively functional take-back and recycling system (Africa Clean Energy, 2019). However, for most developing countries, there is generally a lacklustre approach in dealing with mounting e-waste

problem which is of great concern and is a setback in the overall global effort of managing the increasing volumes of e-waste. A report highlighting the scenario in Asia, singles out legislation and enforcement of specific laws addressing e-waste management as being a major overarching challenge (Honda et al., 2016; Borthakur & Sinha, 2013). The developing countries are beginning to establish e-waste management practices and regulatory frameworks but most are at their elementary stage and often, are substantially inadequate in effectively tackling the e-waste menace (Borthakur & Sinha, 2013; Muhani, 2012; Mmereki et al., 2015).

Kenya lags behind in several aspects of e-waste management. For example, a paltry 10% of e-waste generated in the country is managed properly yet vision 2030 aspires to have high economic and social development while prioritising sustainable environment (NEMA, 2011). Despite having achieved certain legislative milestones, Kenya is yet to fully implement and enforce e-waste specific policies and legislation that effectively facilitate sustainable e-waste management (Africa Clean Energy, 2019; Anyango & Munyugi, 2018; Muniafu & Miya, 2016, Chege, 2021; NEMA, 2011).

WEEE is a cross-cutting issue that touches on several ministries, departments and government agencies (MDAs) and its management is done through various guidelines, standards and regulations from the MDAs. Currently, e-waste management in Kenya is governed by several acts, that include the Environmental Management and Co-ordination (Amendment) Act, 2015 and the Sustainable Waste Management Act (2022). These acts among other provisions, establishes the legal framework for management and conservation of the environment as well as the handling of hazardous waste and pollutants both at the national and county levels (NEMA, 2011). Further, National ICT policy developed by the Ministry of Information Communication and Digital Economy (MoICDE) and published in the year 2019 underscores the government's commitment to formulate policies and regulations for sustainable electronic waste management (Wambui, 2021).

A more recent endeavour undertaken by the Kenya government in the implementation of specific e-waste regulation is the development of the 'National E-Waste Management Strategy' which is a five-year blue print which among other aspirations, is aimed at enhancing regulatory framework to facilitate effective and sustainable management of e-waste at the county and the national levels (Khaduli, 2022).

Despite these efforts, Kenya's response to the global issue of e-waste has been slow. Apart from deficiencies in legal and policy framework, management of e-waste in Kenya grapples with other multiple challenges, ranging from illegal influx of e-waste to lack of adequate awareness among key stakeholders (Otieno & Omwenga, 2015). There is also lack of appropriate infrastructure and technology to support collection, transportation and recycling of e-waste (Omari, 2018). These shortcomings and deficiencies have given rise to increased risks to the environment and human health as a result of improper handling of e-waste.

In a country where robust and sustainable e-waste management system is lacking, important parameters such as e-waste volumes and sources cannot be established and consequently the extent

of e-waste situation cannot be accurately determined (MoEF, 2019). This exposes Kenya to vulnerabilities such as being dumping sites for e-waste by other countries.

Effective e-waste management depends on implementing strategies that involve close collaboration with key stakeholders in the industry (Islam, et al., 2018). The number of actors in e-waste management value chain is enormous as compared to the other solid waste presenting yet another bigger challenge for the country (Khetriwal & Jain, 2021).

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE.

The landscape of e-waste management in Kenya has experienced notable shifts over the years, particularly in how e-waste is managed from the consumer end all the way up to disposal. The main objective of the study is to gain an understanding of the current state of e-waste management aspects and identify inherent challenges and gaps with a view of proposing recommendations based on global good practices, outlining the steps that the Kenya government can adopt to ensure sustainable and safe handling of e-waste.

3. METHODOLOGY

There is a dearth of published information concerning e-waste management in Kenya. This notwithstanding, we endeavoured in this study to use the available data from multiple secondary sources. Given that the primary intention of the research is to provide insight based on a broad understanding of the subject matter, we begin by looking at selected aspects of e-waste management from the global perspective We reviewed relevant literature in academic materials, scientific research reports, technical manuals, government reports and reports by developmental agencies. Regarding the Kenyan perspective, we relied mainly on articles and reports from the Kenya government, international organizations and agencies, newspaper publications, personal sources as well as academic literature.

When selecting the sources, we considered the reputation of journals and publishers, and the dates of publication. The set criteria excluded articles lacking publication dates, those with unclear authorship and publications released prior to the year 2011 .

Our rationale for using the year 2011 as cut-off date for source inclusion is informed by study findings indicating a surge in mobile subscription in Kenya from 114,000 in the year 2000 to 24.9 million in the year 2010 and 28 million in 2011, foreshadowing subsequent increase in utilization of electronic devices (Cherutich, 2013, Oteri et al.,2915). Given that mobile phones constitute a major source of e-waste, it is reasonable to conclude that e-waste issue became prominent in Kenya around the year 2011 up to the present day (Omari, 2018).

Using search keywords (individually or in various combinations) such as e-Waste, Electronic Waste, WEEE, Management, Developing Countries and Kenya, we selected relevant literature mainly from online journals, archival databases and websites.

4. . RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. E-Waste Management, Kenya Scenario

The world's most pressing environmental concern is centred around developing countries because of their vulnerability and the level of preparedness to address environmental issues. These issues include climate change and environmental pollution arising from sources such as WEEE, plastic waste, and toxic effluents (Mosonik, 2022; Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). The negative effects of these developments on the environment are enormous and some are irreversible.

Kenya in its vision 2030 blue-print envisioned a country with efficient and sustainable waste management system through strategies that involve proper handling and recycling of waste (NEMA, 2015). While there has been some steady progress toward achievement of the objective, significant tangible results have not been realised so far (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). The country continues to grapple with serious ecological and environmental crisis, ranging from high level of pollution of water bodies by toxic effluents to increasing influx of WEEE from other countries (Wangari, 2023; Anyango & Munyungi, 2018) .

Each year, Kenya currently generates an estimated 17,000 to 51,3000 metric tonnes.of e-waste, and there is potential for these figures to rise to unsustainable levels if adequate management strategies are not implemented (Shevchenko et al., 2019, Ofuya & Mulinge , 2023, Waema & Mureithi, 2008, Kwame, 2021).

Kenya has shown some level of good will by developing and implementing several strategies at the national level that includes appropriate legislation, relevant policies, standards and regulation that guide the sustainable management of e-waste.

Private actors and non-governmental organizations have also come on board to assist the government in the environmental conservation and protection initiative. For example, Electronic Waste Initiative (EWIK) has been instrumental in raising awareness among the youth on proper recycling of e-waste through repairing of faulty laptops. WEEE centre, a company located in Nairobi engage in recycling and proper disposal of e-waste (Africanews, 2023).

Despite all these efforts, the challenges seem persistent and has become increasingly pronounced at the county levels. where similar initiatives are beginning to take shape. Several counties including Bungoma, Nakuru and Machakos counties have taken the lead in addressing these challenges. Working in collaboration with NEMA, the Nakuru county administration has devised plans for establishing official collection centres for e-waste while Machakos county has already developed an act that specifically addresses the issue of e-waste (Khaduli, 2023; Kenya Law, 2016)

WEEE enters Kenya illegally through porous borders and are also generated locally through imports of EEE. mainly from China (Muniafu & Miya, 2023). Several government initiatives and programs have largely and indirectly contributed to the sudden increase in volumes of e-waste in Kenya. For instance, the Digital Literacy Programme (DLP) for public primary schools introduced millions of electronic devices in the country in 2017 and subsequent years. (Ministry of Information, Communication and Digital Economy (MoIDE), 2023). Soon, other government programmes like the Constituency Innovation Hubs (CIH), Jitume, Ajira Digital, Made-in-Kenya

Smartphone will lead to importation and assembly of more electronic devices to be used for accessing online content and government e-services (MoIDE, 2020,).

A baseline survey conducted to establish the status of e-waste in Nairobi highlighted the level of uncontrolled disposal of e-waste. It revealed that up to 50% of e-waste from refurbishers are sold to the informal market for recycling, where it is often treated in rudimentary manner (Muniafu & Miya, 2016). The unregulated private sector also participates in the recycling process. but often lack the requisite infrastructure and skills for proper and safe treatment of e-waste (Omar, 2019.). A similar study showed that, 40% of e-waste in Nairobi is disposed of alongside other solid waste without separation (Kaloki, 2014). The management of e-waste is mainly done by the informal *Jua Kali* sector, which engages in the economic activity to meet and sustain their subsistence requirements. This sector consists mainly of metal scrap dealers and component scavengers who look for valuable materials for repairing other faulty EEE or re-sale in the second-hand market. Metal scrap dealers usually cherry pick for metals such as aluminium, steel, copper and iron for export. According to one study, the scrap dealers handle about 18% of e-waste in Kenya (Kaloki, 2014).

The *Jua Kali* artisans also engages in the pre-treatment process of e-waste where they remove easily detachable and re-usable parts (Ofuya & Mulinge). The dismantling and segregation is done manually and under unregulated environment and without proper protection for the workers (Muniafu & Miya, 2016). In a study carried out in Nairobi, only 3% of informal workers were reported to be wearing safety gears while working, and most of the workers were unaware of the health risks posed by e-waste. This lack of awareness is also observed among consumers who have been shown to be unaware of health and environmental effects of e-waste (Kaloki, 2014)

Besides the lack of awareness, several studies have identified lack or weak policy and legal framework, limited technical know-how, insufficient infrastructure, improper collection system, and poor disposal methods as the main setbacks in the proper management of e-waste in Kenya (Ofuya & Mulinge , 2023, Kwame, 2021).

NEMA the lead agency in Kenya responsible for environment conservation has been criticised for its inability to effectively address the pollution in the country. NEMA was established by EMCA act, 1999 with the legal mandate of implementing government polices on environment, yet its impact has not been felt and has been termed as ‘toothless’ it terms of conservation efforts with the main challenges being inadequate financing, under-staffing, competition with other government agencies and, issues related to corruption. (Wangari, 2023)

4.1.1. E-waste Generation

Accurate data on the volumes of e-waste generated globally every year is not easy to obtain partly due non-standardized manner of defining what constitutes e-waste (Mmereki, 2015). The global figures were approximated to be around 53.6 million metric tonnes in 2019, with a projected increase to about 74 million metric tonnes in the year 2030. Unfortunately, only 17.4% of this is properly managed which underscores the sorry state of affairs (Forti et al, 2020). The numbers

vary between countries depending on factors such as economy of the country and population growth (Srivastav et al, 2023, Forti et al., 2020).

In Kenya, the available data shows that about 17,000 to 51,300 metric tonnes of e-waste is generated annually, and just between 1% to 17% is recycled or managed properly (UNEP,2014 Amadala, 2019). In the year 2012, e-waste in Kenya was estimated to be about 3000 metric tonnes and had grown 17 times more by the year 2021 (Africanews, 2023). Due to a large portion of e-waste being handled sub-optimally alongside other municipal waste, most of it end up in places like Dandora dumpsite and Nairobi River. Scavengers recover whatever is valuable for reuse. They may also re-sell this salvaged items or components to middle men with knowledge of the market of the recovered e-waste materials (Omari, 2018).

Several recent activities and events have led to an increased generation of internally or domestically generated e-waste in Kenya. With the advent of Covid -19 pandemic. most business were compelled to adopt the use of digital devices and in Kenya business are known to contribute substantial amount of e-waste (Adejumo, 2021). The government has also intensified the use of digital platforms for delivering services and promoting green energy, all of which will collectively lead to increased use of EEPs.This foreshadows increased generation of e-waste in the near future (Orucho; 2023). Other government led initiatives include programmes such as DLP, Jitume, CIH that are all contributing to intensified use of ICT devices such as laptops, desktops and smart phones (Onyango & Munyungi, 2018)

Despite the Bamako convention prohibiting imports of hazardous waste, additional e-waste is generated through illegal imports from other countries or through refurbished EEPs from countries like China and Europe (Anyango & Munyungi, 2018; Mwathi, 2014).

4.1.2. Collection of WEEE

Collection of e-waste is a challenge world over with recent statistics showing that only 12% of phone-based e-waste is collected in developed countries (Tanskanen, 2013). Studies further show that even in countries with established e-waste management systems collection of e-waste is still a big challenge (Forti; 2020).

In Kenya, there are no good functional collecting schemes or public infrastructure for collection of e-waste (Ofuya & Mulinge; 2023). For instance, in Nairobi, less than half of e-waste generated daily ends up being collected and mainly by the informal sector who do so in none structured way (Ofuya & Mulinge , 2023).

Studies indicate that collection of e-waste from homes and municipal dumpsites is mostly done by informal collectors who are low skilled personnel and who are often exploited (Ofuya &Mulinge) Efforts to implement formal take-back model, initiated by Safaricom and Nokia to encourage the collection of e-waste from phones for safe handling and disposal, faced challenges primarily due to lack of legislative support (NEMA, 2010). The system entailed bringing back EoL phones to designated collection points in Nairobi and other specified parts of Kenya (Ogembo, 2010).

Lack of formal collection mechanism has resulted in the accumulation of large stocks of e-waste at the consumer premises (Otieno & Omwenga 2015; NEMA, 2010).

While it is the responsibility of the government to develop guidelines that regulates the collection of e-waste, the enforcement of these regulation is weak and NEMA has been termed as a ‘toothless dog’ in this regard (Muniafu, 2016).

Recently, WEEE centre partnered with Carrefour stores in Nairobi County and The Eldoret National Polytechnic in Uasin Gishu county to expand its collection network and promote effective collection and pre-treatment of e-waste (WEEE centre, 2023). Previously, WEEE centre had been involved in collection of e-waste from government offices, corporate firms and second-hand dealers for safe disposal (Ngila, 2020,). with collection centres in Kisumu and Nakuru (Kenya News Agency, 2020)

To improve collection, Kaloki (2014) recommends in his study that a proper national and institutional collection system is vital and should be put in place. NEMA is mandated by law to establish such a system that provides effective collection of e-waste by implementing directives such as extended producer responsibility (EPR) (Kimeli;2014). EPR is a strategy that places the responsibility of e-waste collection, treatment, recycling and disposal on the producer or manufacturer of EEPs (Gupt & Sahay, 2015).

Proper collection of e-waste can be done by individuals or registered groups who are trained and licensed to work within a regulated framework. The lack of regulation and structured collection systems means one can deliver to any interested buyer for any agreed pay which encourages exploitation. One barrier that consumers face in delivering e-waste to collection centres is the distance from their homes to the collection point. This is as per the study carried out in Kenya by CDC investment works to establish how consumers manage e-waste. (Bella, 2021) . In light of this, consumers would prefer to be given incentives in form of rewards or compensation in order for them to deliver e-waste to the centres.

A five year strategic plan developed by the government of Kenya is expected besides other things to guide in the building of capacity in a proper collection system for sustainable management of e-waste at the county and national level governments (KiPPRA ,2019).

4.1.3. Product Recovery

Product recovery is commonly understood as ‘re-use’ or refurbishment and is the second in the hierarchy of e-waste management strategy after ‘reduce’ which prioritises the reduction of hazardous substances or pollutants is especially during the design stage of EEE (Modoi & Mihai, 2022).

Key among the commitments that the government of Kenya has shown towards the promotion of product recovery is through the adoption of National Solid Management Strategy which aims besides other objectives to promote the re-use of products (Ofuya & Mulinge , 2023).The take-back system initiated by Safaricom representing the private sector, was instrumental in pursuing this objective. The scheme supported the re-using of phones and related accessories (Cherutich, 2013).WEEE Kenya is a company that was initially licensed to collect e-waste, mainly computers for refurbishment and re-distribution to Kenyan schools. The collected e-waste was added value then re-sold to for re-use (Kulecho & Khan, 2012).

Ofuya & Mulinge (2023) noted that due to availability of cheap devices consumers opt to buy new ones instead of repairing, stating that 70% of those who take EEPs for repairs were not willing to pay anything more than 20% the cost of the new EEE. Considering this consumer behaviour, a study conducted by Omari et al.(2011) in Nairobi, Kenya, revealed that 37% of people ended up disposing of their WEEE due to the high cost associated with repairing the devices. Bella (2021) alluded to the stockpiling of e-waste in homes as due to the lack of service and maintenance contracts and the low monetary value of the products which makes it uneconomical to repair.

It has been observed that recovery and re-use of EEPs can significantly reduce the emission of major greenhouse gases (Park et. Al., 2019). Preventing e-waste generation, reducing its volume, and promoting re-use can therefore alleviate the phenomena of environmental pollution and climate change. Additionally, manufacturing using re-cycled materials has been shown to require less energy compared to virgin materials resulting in a corresponding reduction in the consumption of fossil fuels (Seif et al., 2023).

4.1.4. Material Recovery

Kenya's biggest challenge at the moment is that a large portion of e-waste is managed informally, where materials and components are harvested for use in repair of EEE or for re-sale to scrap metal dealers (Muniafu & Miya, 2016). In this informal system, the downstream vendors selectively cherry pick and dismantle specific EEPs with the intention of recovering valuable parts from the discarded WEEE (Otieno & Omwenga, 2015). However, in this selective process, only e-waste with presumed value, as assessed by the scavengers is salvaged while the rest is improperly disposed of. The consequence of such an approach is that low value WEEE is thrown away with some intrinsic valuable materials left unrecovered.

One of the objectives of proper management of e-waste is the harvesting of precious and useful materials such as palladium and platinum for re-use. This process must be conducted in a safe environment with minimal negative effects on the environment (Modoi & Mihai, 2022).

There is a proposal that the implementation of circular economy model would address the aspects of resource optimization which advocates for re-use of materials thus minimizing environmental pressure. The circular economy approach seeks to maintain the value of materials by circulating them within the system loop. (Koech & Munene;2020; Bella, 2021)

Tanskanen (2013) says proper recycling process enables the recovery of valuable materials which serves as a source of secondary material supply for use in manufacturing new products which in a way injects efficiency in the value chain. This recovery of materials averts the use of primary raw materials which is a saving of natural resources. In most cases this cannot be effected because consumers are not aware of the saving in material in a proper recycling system that involves material recovery hence lack of support (Tanskanen, 2013). The presence of rare and valuable materials like gold, silver, palladium and platinum and non-precious ones like iron, copper, steel and aluminium in WEEE has given birth to what is known as 'urban mining' where these materials

are extracted from e-waste in landfills often found in urban areas (Franz & Silva, 2021; Massa & Archodoulaki, 2023).

4.1.5. Disposal

Kwame (2021) noted, that one of the reason things may get out of hand in the management of e-waste in Kenya is because of lack of proper disposal systems. Many people would easily dispose of e-waste without considering the consequence of their irresponsible behaviour, which can lead to environmental and health hazards.

Ofuya and Mulinge (2023) highlights that recycling activities are predominantly carried out by the informal sector whose methods of disposal include re-selling, dumping in the dust bins or rivers, or burning them in the open air.

Upon reaching their EoL, e-waste, especially from phones have different proportions of substances which complicates disposal process. In Nairobi, a significant portion of e-waste comprises phones, with a majority of them being used by repair technicians to scavenge for parts to fix faulty devices. Surprisingly, up to 75% of EoL electronics received by repair shops, which cannot be repaired or re-used in any way, end up being dumped indiscriminately with other solid wastes (Cherutich, 2013). When asked on how they would dispose of their products once they were no longer in use, a study conducted in Kenya by Bella (2021, observed that 40% of the consumers would choose to burn them while another 40% would simply bury or dump them anywhere.

The disposal of e-waste by Kenya government MDAs usually follow established rules on procurement and disposal of items, where the items are bonded together with other items and disposed of through a competitive bidding process (Gathuka, 2013). Unfortunately, WEEE are disposed of as scrap metals in most cases.

In a study conducted by Anyango and Munyuki (2018) it was established that most disposal of e-waste was done using municipal solid waste disposal systems (MSW) and extended storage within institutional premises.

Private companies and corporations may dispose of unused electronic and electrical items as donations to needy groups. There are no regulations currently in place governing e-waste donations.

All formal recyclers in Kenya are based in Nairobi which include WEEE Kenya with recycling capacity of 10,000 tonnes per year (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). WEEE centre handle e-waste from government institutions and private enterprises. Upon reaching their premises, WEEE is pre-treated where some parts like the motherboards are shipped abroad to companies that have infrastructure to carry out proper recycling and disposal (Ongaji, 2023). The formal disposal process usually has the residue fractions either incinerated or buried in designated landfills in a fully controlled manner.

It is important to note that any disposal option has its own environmental effects that must also be managed well. For example, disposal by incineration causes air pollution (Tanskanen, 2013) And, the lack of proper disposal mechanisms ends up endangering both human and livestock.

4.1.6. Legislation and Policy

The legal framework for e-waste management in Kenya is currently established through ‘Environment Management and Coordination Act’ (EMCA) of 1999 (Revised 2015) and ‘Waste Management Regulation’ (2006) (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). The former Act provides for coordinated approach in the implementation of existing environmental laws for example, requirements for mandatory compliance of environmental regulations and provisions for handling of waste including disposal (Anyango & Munyungi, 2018). Under the Act, NEMA is given legal mandate to issue and revoke certificates required for carrying out safe and sustainable management of waste (Macharia, 2014). Gathuka (2013) observes that while the Act is important in environment conservation systems, it may fail because it relies heavily on coercion without consideration of other factors such as weak enforcement instruments and financial resources required to impose regulations.

In 2010, NEMA developed ‘Guidelines for E-waste Management in Kenya’. The guidelines were to form the basis for development of regulations that would facilitate enforcement of standards and procedures in the safe and sustainable management of e-waste in Kenya. It provided guidance and set practical strategies for proper handling and treatment of e-waste by all stakeholders (Onderi, 2011).

The Kenya government has further demonstrated commitment by enacting laws such as the ‘Sustainable Waste Management Act, 2022’. Under the provisions of this act, manufacturers of EEPs are obligated to take responsibility of their products for the entire life cycle including proper disposal of e-waste (Kenya Law, 2022). This Act also provides a framework for management initiatives and actions on waste, in both the national and county governments. This includes developing key guidelines and policies, allocation of roles and responsibilities for various actors and handling of producers regarding EPR scheme, among other measures (Simidi, 2022).

The draft ‘Environmental Management and Coordination (E-waste management) Regulations, 2013’, stipulates mandatory procedures for all round safe management of e-waste all the way up to disposal and coordination of various initiatives in the overall objective of its proper management (NEMA, 2013). The regulations has provisions for control of EEPs into the country and management of their EoL.

In the year 2019, MoEF did another draft for ‘National E-waste Management Strategy’ that yet again sets out a 5 year plan for mitigating and managing e-waste. Kenya has also adopted the National Solid Waste Management Strategy which is geared towards ensuring healthy and safe environment for the citizen of Kenya through sustainable management of solid waste (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023).

Cherutich (2013) has highlighted the need to develop effective e-waste policies and regulations that can be enforced both at the county and national level Kenya governments. The situation in India was once similar to Kenya where there was existence of specific legislation on e-waste but lacked in efficacy. However, over time, India progressively amended its regulation, specifically on EPR to improve on the performance (Borthakur & Govind, 2017). EPR lifts the burden of

management of EoL products from government administration to producer or manufacturer or their agents called extend producer organizations (EPOs)

4.2. WEEE Management Challenges in Kenya

E-waste management in Kenya is currently facing numerous challenges and there is an urgent call to find an appropriate way of dealing with the challenges before they spiral out of control (Otieno & Omwenga, 2015). Lack of proper infrastructure, low awareness levels, inadequate technology or expertise for proper management of e-waste, inadequate funding and lack of stakeholder collaborations are just but a few of the challenges dogging the effort of proper management of e-waste in Kenya (Anyango & Waema, 2013). Ofuya & Mulinge (2023) identified dumping, inefficiencies within the public services concerned with environmental conservation, unregulated and uncoordinated actors, lack of proper support mechanism for collection of e-waste, lack of legislative framework for controlling influx of second-hand products, ineffective implementation of existing regulations and legislations, as well as shortage of technical expertise.

Just like the other developing Nations, Kenya has to grapple with e-waste management challenges of the decade, partly due to the need to develop young industries and the increasing technological advancements of EEE (Hossain et al., 2015).

4.2.1. Rate of Increase in e-Waste Volumes

The primary concern in the management of e-waste apart from its environmental impact is the rate of increase in e-waste volumes (Borthakur & Sinha, 2013). With the rapid development of more powerful, convenient and aesthetically attractive models of electronic devices and electrical appliances, EEPs quickly become technologically obsolete leading to the rise in purchase of new and refurbished products (Muniafu, & Miya, 2016). New EEE destined for Kenya mainly originates from China while refurbished units may come as donations from countries such as the UK (Muniafu & Miya, 2016).

Modern consumers of EEE exhibit insatiable consumerism behaviour as compared to previous generations making the turn-over of EEPs to continuously grow as the lifespan EEPs becomes increasingly shorter (Bhutta, et al 2011; Muniafu & Miya, 2016). The increasing disposable incomes among the millennials adds another dimension for the rising volumes of e-waste in Kenya (Asante, 2019)

Globally, the challenge of e-waste stems from the fact that it is the fastest growing waste stream with growth rate of 3-5% per year (Ambetsa, 2021; Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). This is approximately three times the growth rate of solid municipal waste (SMW) (Ambetsa, 2021; Geoffrey et al., 2022) and accounts for about 1 % of SMW in developing countries (Muniafu & Miya, 2016).

The current levels of e-waste in Kenya is not well documented but generation per year was approximated to be about 51,000 tonnes in the year 2021 (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). The growth volumes is proportional to a set of valuable materials as well as hazardous materials they contain (Muniafu & Miya, 2016; Balde, et al 2015). The common trend observed in many developing

nations is the disposal of e-waste without careful consideration of the value and potential hazards that the components possess (Muhani, 2012).

Access to low quality and cheap electronic goods, along with increasing population has led to drastic increase in the number of EEE imported from China and European countries in the last few years (Asiimwe, 2012; Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). Increased adoption of ICT by both private and public sectors for various applications because of Covid-19 pandemic also contributed to the rising volumes of EEE (Adejumo & Oluduro, 2021). There has also been a rapid expansion and improvement of telecommunication services recently that has seen Kenyan consumers increase the use of mobile telecommunication equipment and application of computer devices such as smartphones in households (Cherutich, 2013; Omwenga & Otieno, 2015). It is normally presumed that an increase in the acquisition and utilization of mobile communication devices has a corresponding proportionate increase in the volumes of e-waste generated. Mobile phone users for example, rose from 24.9 million users in 2010 to 28 million in 2011 and may have increased more rapidly in the subsequent years. Coincidentally, this was the period that a national conference with a focus on e-waste management took place in Kenya (Kulecho & Khan, 2012).

The increasing volumes of WEEE in developing countries such as Kenya is also thought to be because of large imports of second hand EEPs through legal and illegal channels Studies indicate that about 50% of computers sold in Kenya are second hand, further exacerbating the e-waste build up crisis (Kulecho & Khan, 2012).

4.2.2. Unmanaged Entry Points of e-Waste Influx

The increasing numbers of EEE will result in the generation and accumulation of e-waste at EoL to an extent that will pose a challenge in management. Besides the internally generated e-waste, Kenya suffers the influx and proliferation of e-waste from outside the country. Studies indicate that up to 80% of e-waste in developed countries find their way into developing countries for disposal with. Kenya being one of the destinations (Lundgren, 2012). Much of the entry of e-waste into Kenya is facilitated by lack of or weak WEEE specific regulations allowing both legal and illegal e-waste trading and trans-boundary movements (Franz & Silva, 2022). It is acknowledged that Kenyan legislation on e-waste has not been adequate to cause good results in e-waste management effort (NEMA, 2010). Some junk EEPs are still entering in form of donations and end up being e-waste in a short time (Otieno & Omwenga;2015; Franz & Silva, 2022). Lately second hand EEPs that cost a fraction of new the products have gained entry through e-commerce platforms such as *Jumia* and *Kilimall*. Entry of WEEE into Kenya as a developing economy is further fuelled by the high cost of treating e-waste in the developed nations. The increasing numbers of obsolete EEPs will encourage and promote the informal treatment of WEEE putting the Kenyan population at risk due to the pollution of environment. To successfully manage e-waste, proliferation and transfer of used devices and appliances to developing countries must be checked with stringent legal infrastructure both at the local, regional and international level (Franz

& Silva, 2022). If not checked, WEEE would put Kenya in unproportionate burden in the coming years due to increasing rates of influx (Munyugi & Anyango, 2018).

4.2.3. Lack of Incentives for Re-use of e-Waste

Structured repair and re-use or re-manufacturing is considered a sound approach to management EoL electronics. In Kenya, lack of formal supportive legislation for repair and re-use of EoL electronics poses a challenge to the economy and the environment. Repairing of EEE maintains their value for a long time which is one way of optimally utilising resources.

WEEE is dismantled and re-used in Kenya by backstreet traders mostly found in urban centres who determine the value of e-waste and pay collectors based on their assessment. The collectors are often underpaid and work in poor conditions because of lack of relevant legislation (Otieno & Omwenga, 2015, Omar, 2019).

The European Union 'Circular Economy Action Plan' promotes repair of EEE by addressing the need and the right to repair such as upgrading software and advocating for reparation of EEE (Corsini et al., 2020). Some companies in Kenya attach a lot of value to the issue of proprietary software as a means of continuously earning revenues through periodical updates which is a challenge to be addressed in the whole process of managing e-waste.

Muniafu and Miya (2016) suggested that incorporating a few incentives could foster the practices of proper e-waste management through reuse. Some incentives to promote sustainable reuse and repair of EEPs can be in the form improving occupational safety and, upgrading skills of informal workers, and creating an environment that encourages re-use and repair of EEE through legislation, access to spares, and negotiating for good remuneration.

4.2.4. Lack of e-Waste Treatment Infrastructure

Like in many developing countries WEEE in Kenya is treated informally using means such as open air burning which has been classified as the most environmentally detrimental form (Wang et al., 2020). The easiest and popular way that *Jua Kali* traders in Kenya extract copper from electrical cables is through open air burning. The process releases hazardous airborne pollutants to the atmosphere (Balasubramanian & Karthik, 2016). The informal *Jua Kali* sector again cannot manage e-waste in sound manner because they lack technological skills and capacity to treat the waste effectively and safely (Omar, 2019).

As compared to the handling of metallic scrap, the complex composition of substances with different economic value integrated in e-waste materials makes it extremely hard to recycle and manage appropriately and would require complex infrastructure (Tanskanen, 2013, Shevchenko, et al., 2019). Kenya currently does not have the kind of formal recycling system that segregates and separates useful material from non-valuable materials (Anyango & Munyugi, 2018). A lot of WEEE is handled by the informal sector and a few private treatment facilities which manage very small volumes as compared to the volumes generated (Anyango & Munyugi, 2018). For instance,

WEEE centre in Nairobi has managed to handle about 10,000 tonnes since inception. The centre dismantles, separate and export WEEE under controlled and safe environment.

Kimeli (2014) identified poor infrastructure as being an obstacle to sound management of e-waste in Kenya. Yet this far, Kenya is yet to fully recognize recycling as a viable industry especially for EEEs. The national strategy on e-waste identified the need for the county governments to build capacity in infrastructural system for sustainable collection and management of e-waste (MoEF, 2019).

Muniafu and Miya (2016) states that the reason why up to 68% of consumers stockpile e-waste in their households is primarily because of lack of proper infrastructure in Kenya.

4.2.5. Informal Sector

Globally, 80% of the e-waste is managed by the informal sector (Otieno & Omwenga, 2015). This sector is a key player in Kenya's e-waste ecosystem. The informal e-waste recycling sector are often illiterate on environmental and safety issues. Their only concern being economic gains through sale of valuable components (Wang, et al., 2020). The pretreatment process as done by the sector is rudimentary and often lack proper segregation skills and capacities, They dis-assemble the material using manual techniques and most e-waste end up in municipal dumpsites (International Labour Organization (ILO), 2014).

Recognition of the sector in sustainable e-waste management will address both the occupational and environmental challenge that the workers experience (Lundgren, 2012, Ofuya & Mulinge). Muniafu and Miya (2016) notes that the sector has been neglected in Kenya and has not been given incentives to foster proper e-waste management. This sector hardly receives attention on e-waste management efforts but are often marginalized and harassed by police and municipal law enforcement agencies (Ofuya, 2023).

To facilitate proper management of e-waste in Kenya, there should be an enabling environment for the informal sector to operate and partner with formal social enterprises engaged in the safe handling of e-waste (Bastein et al., 2021).

Informal sector has been shown by research to be strong and effective in collection, dismantling and some functions within the preprocessing (ILO, 2014) It has to be involved and recognized in order to supply the e-waste value chain with secondary materials. Such arrangement ensures that the informal sector receives the necessary training and support from the government leading to mutual benefits for all the parties involved.

4.2.6. Lack of Awareness of e-Waste Risks and Disposal Systems

Numerous studies have reported lack of or inadequate awareness on several aspects of sound e-waste management as being a major challenge (Omwenga & Otieno; Anyango & Munyugi, 2018, Omar, 2019). A study conducted by Kiniti et al (2020) demonstrated how inadequate awareness has a substantial bearing on how people dispose of e-waste. Most people in Kenya treat WEEE

just like regular solid waste and recklessly disposing them of in gardens, rivers and by the waysides (Liza, 2015).

Stockpiling of WEEE in houses and offices has also been traced to having its roots in lack of awareness (Muniafu & Miya, 2016). Taskanen (2016) also says people are not aware that there is a saving in resources such as raw materials whenever e-waste is properly recycled. It is clear that increased awareness in Kenya is vital to ensure impacts of e-waste management is evident at the grass root level.

4.2.7. Partial Compliance to International Conventions

The potential environmental and health risks that e-waste poses globally requires the focused attention and collaboration from all international players. International conventions, treaties and agreements form the basis for governments to consider and develop legislative framework to address local existential and emerging e-waste challenges. Regulatory framework is key in the the whole management process but the right approach has to be employed. The top-down regulatory approach which relies on a central authority for development and control of legislation has been proven ineffective when it comes to international management of e-waste which may respond better to collaborative approach of all stakeholders including private sector, manufactures, etc, who can develop innovative ideas for safe and environmentally sound e-waste disposal approaches (Awasthi et al, 2019; Tetra Tech International Development, 2021). International regulations and conventions serve only as important reference point tools for promoting standardization in the way e-waste should be managed at the local level. They also help in defining specific roles of all parties involved at the global level (Franz & Silva; 2022).

Kenya is a signatory to a number of important international conventions such as the Basel convention on the control of trans-boundary movements of hazardous wastes and their disposal (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023), Stockholm convention on persistent organic pollutants, Bamako convention on the ban on of importation of hazardous substances to Africa (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023).

Partial adherence to international regulatory conventions is another challenge to Kenya's pursuit of sound e-waste management especially on the control of cross-boundary movements (Muhani, 2012). Trans-boundary movement of WEEE due to illegal shipping and donations of equipment nearing EoL is worsening the e-waste problem in Kenya. The illegal entry of EEPs without proper documentation detailing substances they contain inherently hampers the effective implementation of the provisions outlined in the Basel convention.

Lack of enforcement of environmental regulations in Kenya has been attributed to factors such as inadequate funding to the relevant government agencies (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023).

4.2.8. Inadequate Financing or Funding Mechanism

The rate of obsolescence and complexity of materials making up e-waste is high and therefore, financial costs associated with their safe treatment outweigh the anticipated economic gains.

A challenge Kenya is facing when executing policies regarding e-waste management is lack of financing mechanism (Omar 2019; Ofuya & Mulinge; 2023). Government agencies responsible for overseeing the policy implementation often face acute lack of financial resources, hindering their ability to carry out essential activities like enforcing regulations. Enforcement of regulations requires huge funding and where such financial support is lacking, vices such as corruption thrive slowing or completely hindering the implementation process of functional e-waste management (Omar, 2019; Gathuba, 2013).

To circumvent the challenge, sustainable funding mechanisms such as EPR is required where laws obligates the manufacturers or producers to take the responsibility in what is known as ‘polluter-pays’ principle of carrying economic burden of sound e- waste management activities (Tanskanen, 2013)

Kenya has proposed the implementation of EPR system under Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) regulation 2021 which is under development. It will stipulate roles of various actors including EEE producers and how take-back system will be implemented (Macharia,2021).

4.2.9. Culture

Japanese EEE consumers are known to be highly sensitive to e-waste and have developed strong recycling tradition enabling the country to achieve a recycling rate of 75% (Africa Clean Energy (ACE), 2019; Doan et al., 2019). In contrast, Kenyan culture exhibits unique tendency of avoiding responsibility for proper treatment of e-waste. This cultural inclination has led to stockpiling of e-waste in peoples’ houses and warehouses with studies showing that about 50 % of e-waste are kept in homes. This habit presents a lot of danger as some of the WEEE may contain batteries or other hazardous substances that worsens with time leading to issues like battery leaks (Omari, 2019).

The habits are developed and sustained by the emotional value that the owners attaches to the EEE. This emotional attachment, referred to as ‘nostalgic value’ by Tanskanen (2013) arises when EEP is no longer functional or serving its purpose but the owner choses to retains due to financial expenditure incurred in acquiring or the belief that e-waste may be useful in some other way in the future (Balasubramanian, et al, 2016; Omari, 2019). Studies show that most Kenyans would prefer staying with e-waste even after repair technicians have declared them useless (Kimeli, 2014).

Another unique cultural aspect in Kenya that aggravates the problem of e-waste build up in the country is the practise of disposing of EEPs especially mobile phones not because they are no longer functional but because there something technologically better is available in the market and is affordable. This behaviour hasten the speed of e-waste obsolescence.

Moreover, Kenyan consumers prioritise affordability over durability and reliability when choosing to buy EEPs (Asiimwe, 2010). This further compounds the problem of e-waste as most such inexpensive products end up having a relatively short lifespan and yet firms keep importing them to sustain their profits and operation (Muniafu & Miya, 2016).

4.2.10. Inadequate Policy and Legislative Interventions

The inadequate regulatory and policy interventions have largely been blamed as the cause for the poor management of e-waste in Kenya. The deficiency has been singled out as the main reason for the uncontrolled illegal inflows of second hand EEE that has turned Kenya into a dumping ground for e-waste (Omari, 2019).

E-Waste management is anchored in article 42 of the Kenya constitution (2010) which guarantees the rights of every citizen to a clean and healthy environment which must be protected for the benefit of posterity (Opondo, 2020). Other policies and legislation that addresses some aspects of e-waste include, National Environmental Policy (2013), Environmental Management and Coordination Act, 1999 (Revised 2015), Waste Management Regulations (2006), National E-waste guidelines (2011), National Solid Management Strategy (2015) (NEMA, 2014). Others are National E-waste Strategy (2019) and Draft E-waste regulation. National E-waste guidelines of 2011 was aimed at enhancing public awareness as well providing guidance on practical aspect of sound e-waste management (Opondo, 2020). and National ICT policy of 2006 requires vendors or operators to demonstrate readiness to undertake actions aimed at minimising environmental impact caused by their infrastructure (Macharia, 2021). The National ICT Policy of 2019 underscores the potentials of emerging technological advancements but fails to acknowledge some challenges such as buildup of e-waste (MoICT, 2019).

Acts such as Environmental Management and Coordination Act (1999) are often ineffective and have failed to facilitate proper treatment of e-waste for lack of capacities or goodwill by the enforcing agencies (Gathuba, 2013). Waema & Mureithi (2008.) notes that existing policies and legislation does not adequately empower crucial government agencies limiting their capacity to effectively manage e-waste.

The existing regulatory framework don't adequately address issues such as EoL effects of government owned EEE which end up being weakly managed under the Public Procurement and Asset Disposal Act, 2015 (Muniafu & Miya, 2016, Kwame, 2021; Macharia, 2021).

Scrutiny by experts have identified that, despite the existence of guidelines and polices, there is still need for the establishment of laws and instruments that would impose adequate punitive measures to ensure implementation of proper e-waste management requirements (Ngila, 2020; Opondo, 2020,).

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Kenya is already facing a crisis as a result of toxic effluents contaminating its water bodies and climate change impacts. In addition to these issues, emerging challenges related to e-waste management are becoming increasingly apparent. Government programmes and initiatives on ICT have inadvertently promoted the buildup of internally generated WEEE to unprecedented levels, weak regulatory frameworks and porous entry points have further exacerbated the problem by facilitating illegal dumping of WEEE in the country These and other challenges require urgent

attention and a multi-sectorial approach to effectively address them before they spiral to levels beyond control.

While Kenya has made commendable efforts to promote environmental sustainability, critical review of the current state of e-waste management practices in the country revealed existing gaps. We propose the following recommendations, informed by the review, towards the implementation of safe and environmentally sound management of e-waste in Kenya:

- **Establish Collection Centres:** The government should consider supporting and possibly subsidising the initial establishment and licensing of accessible and well distributed localised collection centres where WEEE can be collected and segregated. This will ease logistical issues within the value chain, addressing the challenges associated with an overly centralised system. The implementation of the approach is expected to foster increased collection of e-waste. The government should view this as an initial critical step towards successful implementation of sound e-waste management system in Kenya. The government should also take steps to promote and legally compel consumers, repair technicians and businesses to dispose of e-waste appropriately and in a responsible manner.
- **Public Private Partnership:** To establish a robust and sustainable e-waste infrastructure, the government should consider facilitating collaborations and involvement of key stakeholders at every stage of WEEE life cycle i.e generation, collection, transportation, recycling and disposal. The collaborative effort will mitigate the consequences of e-waste and manage the increasing volumes in the country. It is also important to regularly have social dialogue with private firms, industries, educational institutions, academia, civil societies, experts and local informal players in the development of economically viable infrastructure for e-waste management and in the crafting of supportive policy instruments
- **Review Regulator Framework:** Legislative stock-taking and review with a view of carrying out periodic amendments and reforms will be essential in removing barriers similar to what is currently hampering proper and speedy implementation of directives. Through such audits, weak areas may be identified and improvements made. For example, it has been reported that NEMA is currently lacking adequate enforcement capacities in some aspects.
- **Support EPR Scheme:** EPR strategy can be implemented effectively using PROs, considering their local presence. PROs can be given targets depending on their market share and be required to give regular indicators of their performance. This approach will incentivize PROs to actively participate and be held accountable.
- **Enhance Awareness Programs:** More awareness should be created among the various stakeholders on risks and handling of e-waste. Knowledge of e-waste risks is significant in influencing positive behaviour and responsibility. Elaborate awareness campaigns among the young people in technical colleges through shows and electronic media will enable the upbringing of a generation that is properly schooled on matters e-waste and also facilitate

change in negative cultural behaviours thus making the youth a strong advocacy team. E-waste day, 13th of every October should be marked with debates and discussions in various forums to raise awareness. With enough awareness consumers can themselves be willing to voluntarily supply e-waste to scrap dealers or collection points, but the government has to influence through serious campaigns.

- **Involve Informal Sector:** The role of informal sector has to be recognized and efforts should be made to integrate informal industry into the mainstream e-waste management. The process should include training and empowerment, technically and financially. This will safeguard their health and those of others as well as the environment. Tapping into the numerical pool of *Jua Kali* artisans and involvement of scrap metal dealers could easily be resource of advocacy for clean environment and increasing collection levels. As a government initiative, good and standardised sheds should be built for repair technicians who are licensed so as to promote repair and re-use strategies.
- **Support Jua Kali Sector:** *Jua Kali* workers earn their livelihoods through WEEE and is essential to be protected against overexploitation. To achieve this, recycling activities of *Jua Kali* should be institutionalised and structured to operate within the framework of a government ministry with clear guidelines. This arrangement will elevate *Jua Kali* sector to be a dignified institution where people earn decent income instead of being marginalized socially and economically. Their health and occupational issues need to be guaranteed by the government through formal schemes like NHIF.
- **Adherence to Multilateral Agreements:** There is need to establish a mechanism that ensure compliance with and enforcement of international directives such as Basel and Bamako Conventions, particularly on the importation of second-hand products. Local legislative framework should be enacted that take into consideration the quality of legally imported second hand EEPs and guidelines specifying requirements for EEPs that are allowed for donations locally and how to be treated at EoL.
- **Clarity in Trade Policies:** Stringent policies should be put in place to regulate importation and handling of second hand EEPs. Local legislation should outline requirements for inclusion of information such as, date of manufacture, whether the item is refurbished or not and disclosure of hazardous substances and provision for their acceptance.
- **Introduction of Training Programs on E-waste:** Develop curriculum modules in technical colleges and universities to entrench e-waste management and develop requisite skills for handling e-waste across the value chain. Institutions of higher learning is one of the largest generators of e-waste. Additionally, youth are vulnerable to impacts of e-waste, often due to lack of awareness which leads to irresponsible handling and disposal practices of e-waste.
- **Adopt Circular Economy Model principles:** Transition towards circular economy or system which is the best approach to e-waste management. A government task force should be appointed to spearhead and oversee the implementation of circular economy principles.

The suggestions are expected to enable Kenya government and environmental actors develop adequate intervention measures for addressing the immediate and future challenges in e-waste management.

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